

THE CONCEPT OF CRIMINAL INVASIONS AND ITS TYPES IN THE LEGISLATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Nasibullayeva Nodirabegim Nurbek kizi

General procrature of the Republic of Uzbekistan
mandatory enforcement bureau under Andijan Shahar

Department of State Executive Level 2 lawyer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7776806>

Abstract.

in this article, the concept of crime is covered by the concept of criminal invasions and its types studied in ham, with scientific evidence and examples.

Keywords: crime, invasion of crime, types of Crime, Criminal Code, criminal assault, person, dangerous act, criminal punishment, composition of the crime, murder, preparation for the crime.

In the process of committing an intentional crime, and not just for the purpose of committing crimes committed in order to avoid any criminal encroachments and to guard the interests of society, in many cases, Even is criminally liable for preparing for an intentional crime. That is, an attempt to commit a crime or preparation for it is socially dangerous and a criminal act is committed.

As a person sets himself a certain goal, he submits his will, his own behavior to anashu goal. "As the spider weaves its web, it performs the operations that the Weaver performs. As the Bee builds its nest, it performs the operations that the architect performs. But the difference between the worst Weaver from the most Master spider and the worst architect from the most Master Bee is that the Weaver and the architect do what they need to do in advance in their minds. What other activities of human beings, including an intentional crime, do not apply to such a state only to production?¹

In intentional crimes, when preparing for a crime or an attempt to commit a crime, an individual's law-guarded rights and interests in property, social order and public safety, the Constitutional Order of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other law-guarded objects are threatened or partially damaged. In intentional crimes, the subject may pursue a criminal purpose or prepare to commit it. While darkhol carries out the crimes to be committed according to the guilty situation, he prepares to commit the crime in another case (for example, entering the house and preparing a key to burglary, drawing up a plan to eliminate obstacles, determining at what time the landlord will not be in his house, and hokazos.) In intentional crimes that are committed, Ham may not be able to end an individual's criminal intent for objective or subjective reasons in crimes that are premeditated and committed. In such a case, the crime is not brought to the end of the case, which does not depend on the will of the guilty person. In criminal law, such crimes are said to be non-final crimes. Chapter VI of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the concept of incomplete crimes and their types.

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat kodeksi

According to the content of Article 25 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an act committed by a person is found to be a completed crime if there are all signs of the content of a particular crime.²

According to these above and the content of Article 25 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, intentional crimes can consist of three stages. These are: preparing for a crime: an assassination attempt on a crime and that's it.

As we insisted above, preparing for and attempting to commit a crime and committing them clearly jeopardize interests guarded by law. Accordingly, in such crimes there will be an incomplete criminal composition, that is, the composition of an assassination attempt on a crime.

When the preparation for a crime is expressed in a general way, it creates a clear setting for the commission of a crime. The culprit performs in this the objective side of preparing for the crime.

In the case of a criminal attempt, however, direct criminal enforcement actions begin and may have partially fulfilled the criminal purpose. But not bound by the will of the culprit, Holda is unable to bring the crime to an end. In the case of a completed crime, however, all signs of the content of a particular crime are fully realized.

The first two stages of the criminal stages, namely preparation for the crime and the assassination of the crime, are represented in the theory of the Criminal Code, which summarizes as "preliminary criminal activity". Because in these stages, the crime is not brought to an end, the subject is not able to fulfill the goals of his crime. The stages of the crime are the stages of the implementation of the crime, and in a number of crimes provided for in the special part of the JK there are no stages of the crime. Only in properly intentional crimes will there be stages of crime. The following crimes do not have criminal stages:

- in misdemeanors;
- in crimes committed from extortion.

The crime is carried out in stages, due to the fact that the crime of the right will is prepared in advance, the actions of the culprit are directed to a specific goal, the Will and its actions are subordinated to achieve this goal. Crimes committed from Egri intentional and involuntary will not have criminal stages due to the fact that they were accidentally committed without such signs. The stages of crime are the stages of the implementation of criminal intent. The possibilities of criminal stages are limited, and the preparation for a crime, as a general rule, will exist only in crimes of material content, depending on the case from the form of its commission (malpractice or malpractice).

Such a rule applies to the stage of assassination of a crime, and only in material crimes there will be stages of crime, regardless of whether it was committed from dishonest or dishonesty. For example, a thief enters a warehouse for the purpose of looting property, a mother does not suck choakalok for the purpose of raising her child.

Formal-content crimes, on the other hand, can have stages of crime only in those crimes that are committed through harmfulness. There may be a preparatory stage in formally composed crimes that are committed from malpractice when taken from a theoretical treatise, but hardly occur in practice. Because it is very diyin to prove it first, and the fact that the culprit prepares to commit his criminal act makes it very unlikely that he will be able to fill in the

² O'zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat kodeksi

interest that is duridable by law at risk. Because the very structure of the norms that imply responsibility for crimes of formal composition is dictated by the fact that the beginning of the is complete.

But formal crimes committed through the act may have stages of crime. But in this, a certain time must have passed between preparation and the implementation of the crime. For example, the preparation of a false document for extortion (Article 165 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan), the sending of the subject of an agreed bribe (Article 210) by intermediary or mail and hokazos.

The stages of the crime are practically no matter how much Hech is for what crimes are committed. But it is important in qualifying an act if the crime has not been brought to an end for objective or subjective reasons. If the crime is suspended at the preparatory stage, it is found as preparation for the crime (Part 1 of Article 25 of CC), and if the crime is suspended at the assassination stage, it is found as an attempt at the crime (Part 2 of Article 25)..

According to the stages of the crime committed, the level of social danger is not the same. As a general rule, the level of social danger of assassination in relation to preparation for a crime is higher, the level of social danger of a crime, which is more than complete in relation to the assassination of a crime, is higher. This means that as the crime progresses from one stage to the other, the level of social danger increases as it progresses towards the end. Accordingly, it is important to determine at any stage of the crime, to determine the characteristics and content of the criminal offense, to qualify according to what stage the offense was stopped. If the criminal code is suspended at the stage of preparation for a particular crime provided for in a special part of the criminal code, then the act of Republic of Uzbekistan

Part 1 of Article 25 is qualified by the corresponding norm of the special part of the ending. Where a crime is suspended in the assassination phase, Part 2 of Article 25 of the CC, qualifies by the appropriate norm of the final special part. And the crimes that are completed are qualified only by the corresponding norm of the special part of the CC.³

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat kodeksi.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat kodeksi.
3. O'zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat kodeksi.

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasining jinoyat kodeksi

